

DEVELOPING AND DOING VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY OF THE MOTIVATIONAL FACTOR SCALE OF BEING CHOIR SINGERⁱ

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Abstract:

The main aims of this study are to develop “The Motivational Factors Scale of being Choir Singer (MFSCS)” and define the validity and reliability for Turkish population. This research is descriptive research restricted by the choir singers in Antalya city center. In this study, face to face data collecting method applied to all choir singers (n=653) in Antalya. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was done, and varimax rotation was performed on 40 items for MFSCS and the MFSCS was grouped into seven factors. Whether the data was suitable to this analysis, Kaiser Mayer Olkin and Bartlett Sphericity test results were taken into consideration and then, EFA was performed. Cronbach’s Alpha internal consistency test was applied to the identified sub-factors and overall scale. It was found that CFA parameters were in limits. Pearson Correlations Test was conducted to define the statistical correlation between sub-classes and items. Results have been assessed according to significant level 0.01 and 0.05. As a result, it was founded that Cronbach’s Alpha as 0.928, total explained variance as %65.58 and CFA parameters were in statistically satisfactory limits. It can be concluded that MFSCS has reliability and validity in the estimation of “The Motivational Factors Scale of Being Choir Singer” for the Turkish population.

Keywords: validity and reliability, motivational factors, choir, choir singer, recreation

1. The Motivational Factors of Participating in Recreational Choirs

Music is defined as an important branch of art and has been accepting as a way of explaining themselves as an individual or as a community since the ancient times. In this sense, music as a cultural element has indispensable role in human life as a one of

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the powerful instruments (Coskuner, 2009). Physicians, philosophers, psychologists, psychiatrists and pedagogues use the music to affect individual's mental and physical development with regards to treatment and education since the ancient times (Yavuzer, 2007).

The choir is one of the ways to play music or sing. A choir can be defined as a [musical ensemble](#) of singers (Ucan, 1997). Choirs, singing in a choir, vocal ensembles, choir practice, vocalist, choral rehearsals are the words conjure up all same meanings. Pierce (2003) defines singing in a choir as a solitary occupation, co-occupation or a shared occupation. Singing in choir can be accepted as co-occupation and choirs can be professional and/or amateur (O'Toole, 1994). When leisure occupation defined as an activity that individuals engaged in to enjoy life, (Law, Polatajko, Baptiste, and Townsend, 2002), and as things individuals do to obtain mental wellness, to their volition, to meet personal/group goals of their choosing (Daniel and Manigandan, 2005), singing in amateur choir can be accepted leisure activity and has active recreational effect. In addition to these, while listening to music as a favorite hobby or pastime is globally acknowledged accepted passive leisure, active engagement in recreational music making activities is associated with a host of individual and group benefits (Bittman, 2001; Bittman, Berk, Felten, Westengard, Simonton, Pappas and Ninehouser 2001).

Scientists claim that the needs motivate individuals to do or not to do something. This was known as Maslow Needs Hierarchy. Maslow grouped need in two groups as primary needs (food, security, and belonging) and secondary needs (being with friend, creativity, curiosity, getting rid of ego and building self) (Ibrahim and Cordes, 2002). Lawler (1973) concluded that action of human is the result of psycho-social and physiological outcomes in his expectancy-value model. The relation between behavior and motivation was the main purposes of many researchers to explain "why" a person participates in leisure. The most famous one is Driver's (1983) "Master list of items from Recreation Experience Preference scales and domain", then Manfreda, Driver, and Tarrant (1996) used master list of items to define the motivational factors affecting an individual to participate in active and/or passive leisure activities.

Generally, there are many reasons to affect individuals to participate in any of recreational activities and privately singing in a choir also. Crandal (1980) claims that the personality and the condition have affect to participate in active and/or passive activities, Levy (1979) claims that there is interaction between social conditions and personality which promote individuals to participate in recreational activities. Some others try to explain why people participate in recreational choirs by using motivation theories like; a) Self Determination Theory (Deci and Ryan, 1985), b) the Achievement Goal Theory (Pintrich, 2000), c) Needs Theory (Ibrahim and Cordes, 2002), d) Activity Theory (Engeström, Miettinen and Punamaki, 2003).

In addition to these, there are some studies on defining the motivational factors which motivate individuals for singing in choir. But none of them is based scale as listed below:

- Beck, Cesario, Yousefi and Enamoto (2000) studied the implementation of Singers Emotional Response Scale (SEES) with members of a Professional chorale,
- Sichivitsa (2003) studied students' academic and social integration, self-concept of musical ability, value of music by using The Choir Participation Survey II.
- Bailey and Davidson (2002) studied adaptive characteristics of group singing.
- Bittman, Snyder, Bruhn, Liebfreid, Stevens, Westengard and Umbach (2004) studied the effect of recreational music making on nursing students' burnout and negative mood.
- Bailey and Davidson (2005) studied effects of group singing and performance for marginalized and middle-class singers.
- Cynthia, Guptill and Sumsion, (2009) studied on lived experience of participating in a non-competitive choir as a leisure activity.
- Clift and Hancox (2010) studied the significance of choral singing for sustaining psychological wellbeing.
- Dingle, Brander, Ballantyne and Baker (2013) studied the social and mental health benefits of choir singing for disadvantaged adults.

The importance of current study is to develop Motivational Factor Scale of Singing Choir and defines the validity and reliability for Turkish population.

2. Method

The main aims of this study are to develop "The Motivational Factors Scale of being Choir Singer (MFSCS)" and define the validity and reliability for Turkish population. The scope of this study is restricted to recreational choir singers in city center of Antalya.

2.1 Sampling

The Sampling group of this study consists of 653 participants of 37 amateur choirs. The exact number of the choirs in Center of Antalya was 43 and six choirs were excluded from the study, two of them were professional and four of them did not want to join the survey.

2.2 The tool of gathering data

The questionnaire form derived from Driver's (1983) "Master list of items from Recreation Experience Preference scales and domain" to gather data suitable for the purpose of this study was delivered to the singers before their practice and give them enough time to answer the questions and get it back. The form includes demographic questions and motivational factors. A five-point Likert scale was used and the range covers (1: definitely disagree, 5: definitely agree).

Before performing an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) on the 44 items, six items were excluded from further analyses due to low initial communalities (<0.40). The factorability of the correlation matrix of the remaining 38 items for MFSCS's Kaiser-

Meyer–Oklin (KMO) value was 0.920 and over then the recommended value of 0.6 (Kaiser, 1974), and has a statistically significant value for Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity.

Varimax rotation was performed on 38 items for MFSCS and rotated results were given in Table-1, the factor loadings of all factors were strong and all variables having loadings substantially from only one factor. Seven motivational factors obtained after EFA. Confirmatory factor analysis was done and all fit indices were satisfied.

3. Results

We used EFA method to determine sub-dimensions of factors which motivate persons to singing in recreational choirs. For this, we added 38 items and performed the Bartlett test of sphericity (Chi-square=15124.475, P=0.000) and calculated Keiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy (0.928>0.6) and saw that EFA method is applicable to our data set. Varimax rotation was performed on 38 items for MFSCS and seven factors obtained for 65.582% of the total variance. Motivational factors including factor components, factor loadings, communalities, and descriptive statistics for each item, Cronbach’s Alpha values for the components and all the scale and all the other EFA results are given in Table-1. Motivational Factors are named as follows;

F1: “Renovate/Developed” factor describes the renovated and/or developed skills and it includes “to renovate and improve myself”, “to obtained use the new skills”, “because it gives opportunity to use my skills”, “to add value to my cultural life”, “to add my daily life variety and range”, “to developed my personal and spiritual values”, “to create and developed my spiritual life” and “to add new dimension to my life”. It has “0.908” Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and “11.054” eigenvalues.

F2: “Relaxing as Mentally” defines all the things mental wellness and it includes “to slow down and relax my mind”, “to add positive value to my mental health”, “to have productive work and social life”, “to rest as mentally”, “being in choir makes me happy”, “being in choir felt me good” and “to have a great time”. It has “0.889” Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and “5.248” eigenvalues.

F3: “To be away / Escape” factor defines to be away and/or escaping reasons and it includes “to be away from my family for a while”, “to be away from my work/school for a while”, “to be away from my daily life for a while”, “to be away from gossip and whispering for a while”, “to be away from problems and responsibility of my daily life for a while” and “to be away from the people around me for a while”. It has “0.871” Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and “2.448” eigenvalues.

F4: “Socialization” factor is the physical and emotional relation created between the participant and the others before/during/after the activity and it includes “to meet and talk with new people”, “to do/share something with my family member”, “to be together reconciled individuals”, “to do/share something with my friends”, “to belong to a friend group” and “to be together with the individuals have common hobbies”. It has “0.842” Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and “2.014” eigenvalues.

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Table 1: Factor Analysis of the Motivational Factors of Singing in Choir

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.								0.920		
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity Approx. Chi-Square								15124.475		
								df	703	
								Sig.	0.000	
	Components and Factor Loadings									
Items	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	Com.	M ± SD	
YG01	0.687							0.684	4.01±1.16	
YG02	0.747							0.660	3.99±1.06	
YG03	0.687							0.670	4.12±1.04	
YG04	0.691							0.418	4.25±0.96	
YG05	0.710							0.616	4.05±1.06	
YG06	0.753							0.685	4.01±1.11	
YG07	0.692							0.632	3.76±1.24	
YG08	0.683							0.631	3.76±1.20	
MOR01		0.648						0.611	3.80±1.14	
MOR02		0.671						0.680	4.10±1.03	
MOR03		0.651						0.592	3.90±1.11	
MOR04		0.796						0.639	4.10±1.04	
MOR05		0.661						0.620	4.32±0.98	
MOR06		0.687						0.671	4.27±0.96	
MOR07		0.631						0.656	4.22±1.00	
UZ01			0.696					0.715	2.23±1.39	
UZ02			0.780					0.619	2.56±1.44	
UZ03			0.774					0.648	3.13±1.44	
UZ04			0.749					0.561	3.14±1.52	
UZ05			0.752					0.607	3.04±1.47	
UZ06			0.760					0.614	2.42±1.41	
SOS01				0.619				0.750	3.23±1.25	
SOS02				0.561				0.671	2.91±1.31	
SOS03				0.780				0.689	3.62±1.25	
SOS04				0.781				0.583	3.60±1.23	
SOS05				0.703				0.815	3.24±1.29	
SOS06				0.653				0.657	3.74±1.24	
TSS01					0.857			0.813	2.49±1.35	
TSS02					0.741			0.676	3.00±1.39	
TSS03					0.845			0.774	2.48±1.35	
TSS04					0.759			0.870	2.93±1.43	
MZ01						0.790		0.806	4.46±0.92	
MZ02						0.751		0.464	4.59±0.84	
MZ03						0.758		0.474	4.31±0.97	
MZ04						0.467		0.718	4.05±1.11	
OO01							0.819	0.749	3.22±1.36	
OO02							0.852	0.614	3.30±1.36	
OO03							0.801	0.567	3.36±1.37	
Cronbach's Alpha:	0.908	0.889	0.871	0.842	0.889	0.765	0.891			
Rotated Eigenvalues:	11.054	5.248	2.448	2.014	1.577	1.349	1.231			For all scale.
Rotated variance (%)	13.112	10.899	10.000	9.429	8.740	7.107	6.295			Cronbach's
Rotated cumulative variance (%):	13.112	24.011	34.011	43.440	52.180	59.287	65.582			Alpha=0.928

F5: “Liking Music” factor describes the importance of hobbies in personal life and it includes “because I like singing”, “because I like music”, “because it is in my field of interest” and “to do something about music”. It has “0.889” Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and “1.577” eigenvalues.

F6: “Recognition and Social status” factor describe the importance of recognition and social status as external motivational factors and it includes “because I like singing”, “because I like music”, “because it is in my field of interest” and “to do something about music”. It has “0.765” Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and “1.349” eigenvalues.

F7: “Exemplifying” factor describes the importance of being a model for others and it includes “being a model for family member”, “to be a model for individuals around me” and “to be a model for individuals in the society”. It has “0.891” Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and “1.231” eigenvalues.

Correlations between items and components were given in Table-2. As seen in Table; the correlation results confirm that the items grouped in correct and the relevant sub-dimensions with the highest values after EFA.

Table 2: Pearson Correlations between items and components

Items	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
YG01	0.753**	0.507**	0.083*	0.307**	0.202**	0.380**	0.267**
YG02	0.776**	0.503**	0.106**	0.304**	0.176**	0.372**	0.231**
YG03	0.757**	0.538**	0.075	0.331**	0.165**	0.439**	0.268**
YG04	0.780**	0.615**	0.078*	0.325**	0.066	0.420**	0.242**
YG05	0.799**	0.575**	0.147**	0.381**	0.147**	0.404**	0.246**
YG06	0.841**	0.579**	0.171**	0.399**	0.231**	0.362**	0.311**
YG07	0.764**	0.474**	0.246**	0.366**	0.314**	0.285**	0.287**
YG08	0.792**	0.529**	0.239**	0.411**	0.332**	0.315**	0.310**
MOR01	0.496**	0.711**	0.219**	0.282**	0.190**	0.319**	0.238**
MOR02	0.556**	0.781**	0.092*	0.345**	0.069	0.421**	0.218**
MOR03	0.576**	0.762**	0.195**	0.332**	0.206**	0.374**	0.255**
MOR04	0.550**	0.850**	0.093*	0.331**	0.082*	0.436**	0.212**
MOR05	0.537**	0.793**	0.048	0.331**	0.020	0.528**	0.212**
MOR06	0.545**	0.803**	0.014	0.342**	0.013	0.498**	0.215**
MOR07	0.471**	0.741**	0.047	0.338**	0.034	0.444**	0.211**
UZ01	0.067	-0.009	0.756**	0.177**	0.436**	-0.041	0.189**
UZ02	0.122**	0.071	0.820**	0.193**	0.414**	0.038	0.195**
UZ03	0.173**	0.176**	0.760**	0.224**	0.236**	0.090*	0.210**
UZ04	0.225**	0.202**	0.765**	0.263**	0.284**	0.142**	0.293**
UZ05	0.200**	0.172**	0.774**	0.275**	0.305**	0.082*	0.198**
UZ06	0.084*	0.008	0.805**	0.194**	0.436**	-0.035	0.190**
SOS01	0.253**	0.193**	0.204**	0.674**	0.326**	0.126**	0.328**
SOS02	0.275**	0.193**	0.231**	0.683**	0.350**	0.117**	0.431**
SOS03	0.378**	0.376**	0.222**	0.827**	0.230**	0.287**	0.436**
SOS04	0.425**	0.439**	0.215**	0.834**	0.203**	0.350**	0.429**
SOS05	0.322**	0.277**	0.287**	0.761**	0.362**	0.160**	0.372**
SOS06	0.382**	0.427**	0.114**	0.708**	0.143**	0.315**	0.352**
TSS01	0.183**	0.046	0.420**	0.260**	0.887**	0.023	0.318**

TSS02	0.313**	0.175**	0.322**	0.365**	0.833**	0.111**	0.359**
TSS03	0.174**	0.030	0.449**	0.274**	0.896**	-0.008	0.295**
TSS04	0.258**	0.154**	0.369**	0.351**	0.850**	0.060	0.366**
MZ01	0.329**	0.400**	0.000	0.168**	-0.035	0.789**	0.139**
MZ02	0.334**	0.441**	-0.069	0.151**	-0.069	0.766**	0.097*
MZ03	0.400**	0.435**	0.031	0.191**	0.062	0.820**	0.146**
MZ04	0.379**	0.423**	0.189**	0.378**	0.172**	0.714**	0.291**
OO01	0.285**	0.250**	0.242**	0.430**	0.323**	0.194**	0.880**
OO02	0.324**	0.265**	0.254**	0.494**	0.356**	0.202**	0.937**
OO03	0.334**	0.269**	0.248**	0.502**	0.373**	0.224**	0.902**

4. Discussion

This paper introduces the Motivational Factors Scale of being Choir Singer and defines the validity and reliability of MFSCS for Turkish population.

It can be said that MFSCS is an adequate validity to explain motivational factors to participate in singing choir for the Turkish population. Cronbach's Alpha internal consistency test is 0.928 was applied to the identified sub-factors of scale. The variance explained by these subscales was %65.582 for MFSCS. In addition to these CFA fit indexes were in statistically satisfied limit.

The MFSCS' sub-dimensions can be explained by motivational theories. The Need Theory explains the seven factors of MFSCS. While "To be away/Escaping" and "Relaxing as Mentally" sub-dimensions can be thought in physical needs, "Socialization" and "Renovate/Developed" sub-dimensions fall into Belonging Need and Self-actualisation Need, "Recognition and Social status" sub-dimension is related with Social Status Need and "Exemplifying" sub-dimension is related with Self-actualisation Need. In addition to these, "Liking Music" sub-dimension is related internal motivational factor and "Recognition and Social status" is related external motivational factor can be explained by using Self Determination Theory (Deci and Ryan, 1985). On the other hand, these motivational factors which motivate individuals to sing in choir can be explained by the Achievement Goal Theory (Pintrich, 2000). Participating in choir requires active participation and being active as physically and mentally can be explained by the Activity Theory (Engeström et al., 2003).

The MFSCS' seven sub-dimensions overlap with the Driver's (1983) Master list of items from Recreation Experience Preference scales and domain. At the same time, the results of studies done by Beck et al., (2000), Sichivitsa (2003), Bailey and Davidson (2002, 2005), Bittman et al., (2004), Cynthia et al., (2009), Clift and Hancox (2010), Dingle et al., (2013) confirm the validity of MFSCS.

Finally, results reveal that the Motivational Factors Scale of being Choir Singer were reliable and valid in the estimation of the motivational factors for the Turkish population.

CFA fit indexes values are given in Table-4. All fit indexes value has statistically satisfactory limits. CFA and EFA define the validity and reliability of MFSCS.

Table 3: Factors, Items and Description

Items	Description
Renovate/Developed	
YG01	to renovate and improve myself
YG02	to obtained use the new skills
YG03	because it gives opportunity to use my skills
YG04	to add value to my cultural life
YG05	to add my daily life variety and range
YG06	to developed my personal and spiritual values
YG07	to create and developed my spiritual life
YG08	to add new dimension to my life
Relaxing as Mentally	
MOR01	to slow down and relax my mind
MOR02	to add positive value to my mental healthy
MOR03	to have productive work and social life
MOR04	to rest as mentally
MOR05	being in choir makes me happy
MOR06	being in choir felt me good
MOR07	to have a great time
To be away / Escape	
UZ01	to be away from my family for a while
UZ02	to be away from my work/school for a while
UZ03	to be away from my daily life for a while
UZ04	to be away from gossip and whispering for a while
UZ05	to be away from problems and responsibility of my daily life for a while
UZ06	to be away from the people around me for a while
Socializing	
SOS01	to meet and talk with new people
SOS02	to do/share something with my family member
SOS03	to be together reconciled individuals
SOS04	to do/share something with my friends
SOS05	to belong to a friend group
SOS06	to be together with the individuals have common hobbies
Recognition and Social status	
TSS01	to be recognized and to be recognized by others
TSS02	to have social status
TSS03	wishing recognition
TSS04	because it felt me airs and graces
Liking Music	
MZ01	because I like singing
MZ02	because I like music
MZ03	because it is in my field of interest
MZ04	to do something about music
Exemplifying	
OO01	to be a model for family member
OO02	to be a model for individuals around me
OO03	to be a model for individuals in the society

Table 4: CFA Fit Indexes

X ² / deg. freedom	= 3196.04/644=4,96	SRMR	= 0.075
GFI	= 0.76	CFI	= 0.96
AGFI	= 0.76	NFI	= 0.94
RMSEA	= 0.078	NNFI	= 0.95
RMR	= 0.11	PGFI	= 0.69

Figure 1: Path Diagram of the MFSCS

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